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D7.2 Ethical application documents for JRA3

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19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
JRA	Joint Research Activity
M	Month

Executive summary

VITALISE brings together Living Labs across Europe (and 1 outside Europe in Canada) to create a Thematic ecosystem of Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain, aiming at creating synergies and transnational collaboration opportunities through innovative Joint Research Activities (JRA). JRAs will also serve as the test bed for all the harmonization procedures, for assessing and improving the provided living lab services. JRA3 for everyday living environments will focus on evaluating the usage and applicability of innovative data collection technologies during the various everyday living activities executed inside and outside premises. The results will help to develop harmonized research protocol for developing big data-driven hybrid persona –hypothetical user archetypes created to represent a user community. This document presents the work performed for obtaining ethical approval for the research activities performed in JRA3.

The results indicate significant ethical application process time differences between the countries ranging from few days to over two months. Three different types of the ethical boards were identified: internal, external and mixed boards. Internal entity referring to boards operating within the organization while external board is referring to a board which is not directly associated with the organization conducting the study. Mixed board includes both external and internal actors and can be managed by the research organization or external entity.

All but one VITALISE JRA3 partner have submitted their ethical application. The missing partner (TREBAG) is submitting their application on April. Case studies incorporating AIT, LiCalab, CERTH, AUTH and McGill-UDEM have already received ethical approval. Laurea and INTRAS case studies were asked to do re-submission, which Laurea has already done while INTRAS is waiting for the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products resolution on whether their study is considered as a medical device study before making the re-submission. GAIA has been waiting ethics board decision for over two months but should receive it on April.

As a summary, it is concluded that JRA3 is progressing somewhat as planned, since additional information request are normal during the ethics process. The risk of delays that will have an impact on VITALISE project are not in sight.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP7

The Joint Research Activities will serve as the test bed for all the internal harmonization procedures, for assessing and improving the provided services, as well as the research cases that could be the basis for the external researchers through the trans-national and virtual access procedures.

JRA3 (WP7) for everyday living environments will focus on the collection of big data from everyday living activities inside and outside the house in order to create dynamic personas that are natively multidimensional and will be used for care personalization in real time.

In phase 1 “The Ex Ante and Engaging”, living labs will organize co-creation sessions with healthy adults, adults with minor disabilities, care professionals and city administrators to capture stakeholder perspectives on data collection technologies and approaches in everyday living environments.

The phase 2 “The In Situ and Engaging” five small-scale pilot studies are organized to test innovative interventions or data collection technologies in practice using preliminary harmonized procedures as described by Santonen et al (2022)¹. The five case studies focus on experimentation in different everyday living environments and interventions including smart home environments, virtual reality environments, indoor spaces (home, sport complex, museum, nursing home, living laboratory) and outdoor spaces (outdoor fitness trail, football field). As a result, data triangulation using multiple data sources, investigator triangulation using >1 investigator, theory triangulation using multiple theoretical approaches to interpret the phenomenon, and methodological triangulation using multiple quantitative and qualitative data collection methods will be applied².

The phase 3 “The Ex Post and Engaging” focuses on collectively evaluating case study experiences from a Living Lab operator's point of view. A cross-case analysis grounded on semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions and facilitated workshops will be conducted to identify the challenges and benefits of using the proposed research protocols. The outcome of this research will lead to harmonized procedures and protocols in the context of big data–driven hybrid persona development among health and well-being Living Labs in Europe and beyond.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document will describe all the documents prepared for the ethics approval application of phase 2 of the JRA in WP7, the small scale pilots.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the JRA3 overall research protocol
- **Section 2** make a reference to the informed consent procedures to be followed by all partners during the execution of the JRA3 studies
- **Section 3** describes incidental findings policy
- **Section 4** describes data collection process as well as overview and status of the ethical review process for each case study and partners
- **Section 5** summaries results and provides concluding remarks for this deliverable

¹ Santonen T, Petsani D, Julin M, Garschall M, Kropf J, Van der Auwera V, Bernaerts S, Losada R, Almeida R, Garatea J, Muñoz I, Nagy E, Kehayia E, de Guise E, Nadeau S, Azevedo N, Segkouli S, Lazarou I, Petronikolou V, Bamidis P, Konstantinidis E, : Protocol for Cocreating, Testing, and Seeking Consensus, JMIR Res Protoc 2022;11(1):e34567, URL: <https://www.researchprotocols.org/2022/1/e34567>, DOI: 10.2196/34567

² Denzin NK. The Research Act: A Theoretical Introduction to Sociological Methods. Oxfordshire, United Kingdom: Routledge; 2017:1-368.

2 Informed consent procedures

The informed consent procedures to be followed by all partners during the execution of the JRA3 studies is described in chapter 4 of Deliverable 14.1 as submitted to the commission in M8 of the project.

3 Incidental findings policy

The consent forms which have been submitted for ethics approval include the following incidental findings policy, as described in 5.1.6 of VITALISE Grant Agreement No.101007990:

Main ethical challenge arises when trying to identify when it is ethically permissible or obligatory to disclose or not disclose incidental findings to patients or research participants and how to manage such process.

Four ethical principles are found to be relative to this issue:

1. Principle of respect for persons: which recognizes the fundamental human capacity for rational self-determination;
2. Principle of beneficence: that “calls on professionals to take actions to ensure the wellbeing of others”;
3. Principle of justice and fairness: that requires fair and equitable treatment of all;
4. Principle of intellectual freedom and responsibility: that “...protects sustained and dedicated creative intellectual exploration that furthers scientific progress, while requiring that practitioners take responsibility for their actions.”

In general, an Incidental Finding (IF) is considered to be “a finding concerning an individual research participant that has potential health or reproductive importance and is discovered in the course of conducting research but is beyond the aims of the study. This means that IFs may be on variables not directly under study and may not be anticipated in the research protocol.”

The VITALISE project will adopt and implement the following IFs procedure:

1. The potential participant will be made aware that incidental findings are possible during the process of informed consent. Also, the potential participant will be made aware whether such findings will be disclosed, the process for disclosing these findings, and whether and how participants might opt out of receiving certain types of findings. The potential participant will be given the option to nominate a doctor of their choosing to whom the IFs should be disclosed.
2. If a potential incidental finding is spotted, the researchers will verify such finding. Following verification, the researchers will consult an expert to determine whether a. there is an IF, b. it is significant for the participants health to mandate disclosure
3. If disclosure is mandated, the researchers will take into account the participant’s wishes as expressed in their consent form.

This incidental findings policy adheres to all ethical principles identified as relevant. The policy applies also in cases where the participants lack the capacity for consent, where the legal representative will opt in or out for disclosure of potential incidental findings. The policy will not be implemented in the event that local legislation mandates IFs disclosure regardless of the participant’s wishes (ex. threat of life).

4 Ethical submission processes and files

4.1 Data collection process description

This section presents the processes that have been followed for the ethical submission in each different country and institutions. The similar process was applied for D.5.2 and D6.2. As the

processes vary even within different institutions in the same country each partner was asked to provide the following information:

- Which documents are required for the ethical submission in your case, what are the compulsory and optional documents?
- What is included in each document? Please add a small, generic description of the scope, aim and information included in each document. No need for a detailed structure description on a variable level. Does the document have a specific compulsory structure or can it follow a “free structure”?
- Which is the ethical committee that you submit your ethical application? Please provide a name and structural information (e.g., established internally in your organization, the university committee)
- Website for the ethical committee (if any exists)
- What is the process of submission, dates that the committee is meeting/deciding?
- Do you receive any consultation before the submission? If yes, by whom and what did it include.
- When is the first decision expected?

Furthermore, specific considerations were given to all partners in order to ensure the successful completion of the VITALISE project. More specifically:

- Based on the VITALISE GA, external researchers that will join the Living Lab infrastructures may propose specific analysis to already existing data gathered during the JRAs.
- Synthetic data generated from the data gathered in the JRAs should become available in the RAI system and data discovery portal. Moreover, raw data gathered in the JRAs should become available for analysis in the RAI system and data discovery portal.
- Data for Virtual Access (WP12). “VITALISE will develop access policies based on permissions or licenses granted by data owners, allowing a range of options for contribution and data sharing”. In that sense, please consider if your data could be fully anonymized without losing the required information for your analysis. The pseudo-anonymized data should become available for processing through the VITALISE data discovery portal.

4.2 Case Study 1: Digital Coaching App Impact on Self-efficacy and Well-being

This small-scale transnational pilot will be conducted by AIT (Austria) and LiCalab (Belgium). In this pilot study, The general aim of this case study is to test the digital coach app of the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) by analysing to what extent it can influence individuals’ self-efficacy and well-being by motivating older adults to practice a healthy lifestyle. Moreover, the study will also assess the system’s usability, learnability, and user acceptance in cross –country setting.

4.2.1 Ethical review process in Austria

For the ethical submission, there is no specific template provided. Normally, AIT, Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH delivers a free structured document that basically includes a brief project and study description, including information about the overall research design (e.g., research paradigm, recruitment strategy) the study implementation (e.g., duration, study phases) target group and inclusion criteria (e.g., age or specific requirements like technology usage) as well as more detailed information about data assessment (how is the data assessed and what kind of data is gathered) and data protection (who has access to the data, where is the data stored).

The Ethics Committee of the City of Vienna is responsible for the evaluation of medical research projects within the Vienna Health Care Association (with exception of the University hospital AKH of the City of Vienna). Moreover, the Ethics Committee evaluates clinical trials and medical products/devices outside hospitals.

The study was submitted on 12th January 2022 to The Ethics Committee of the City of Vienna (Annex: Case 1.1 AIT (Austria) Proof of ethics submission). Decision was made on 12th January 2022 by the ethics committee (received 19th of January 2022) stating that the proposed study is not under the Medical Devices Act and therefore, the ethics committee is not responsible in accordance with the Medicines Act, Medical Devices Act and Vienna Hospitals Act to assess the proposed research project (Annex: Case 1.1 AIT (Austria) Proof of ethics approval). Reference was made to other regulations such as the Declaration of Helsinki, publication guidelines, etc. that require the vote of an ethics committee. As a result, AIT can start the proposed study activities.

4.2.2 Ethical review process in Belgium

In Belgium, there are different ethical committees depending on the nature of your study. The WP7 pilot study get ethical approval from the Social and Societal Ethics Committee of the KU Leuven in Belgium (also named SMEC, the acronym of the Dutch name of the ethical committee Sociaal-Maatschappelijke Ethische Commissie). SMEC is an ethics committee set up by the university KU Leuven, and Thomas More (and LiCalab) belong to the greater KU Leuven association. SMEC evaluates research on human subjects that is not related to health science practices and does not include medical or pharmacological procedures. Applications for ethical approval can be submitted to SMEC at any time. SMEC sends out the reviews of the submitted applications twice a month. This means that on average it takes two weeks to receive a decision from the committee. More info can be found on the (English) website³. The documents required in the process includes structured application form, informed consent form, dynamic annex regarding COVID-19. More information regarding the document can be found in KU Kluven "Documents and guidance for your application" webpages⁴.

The study was submitted on 30th November 2021 to SMEC (Annex: Case 1.2 LiCalab (Belgium) Proof of ethics submission). The ethics board concluded on 12th December 2021 that the study protocol meets the set ethical standards with regard to scientific research and therefore decision regarding this protocol is favorable (Annex: Case 1.2 LiCalab (Belgium) Proof of ethics approval).

4.3 Case Study 2: Net Zero Energy Buildings Smart Home Living Lab

This small-scale transnational pilot will be conducted by CERTH (Greece). The aim of this feasibility and acceptability study is to evaluate the impact of physical and cognitive activity performance of older adults in a smart home Living Lab environment using a combined approach of virtual apps and several wearable sensors. This particular small-scale pilot study envisages showing us the benefits of specific types of physical and cognitive exercises combined with Living Lab technological advances. Moreover, the study will also analyze the extent to which it can influence individuals' self-efficacy and well-being by motivating older adults to practice a healthy lifestyle.

4.3.1 Ethical review process in Greece

The Ethical Committee of CERTH is internally established by the Board decision. It consists of five (5) members. At least two of these members, must not be affiliated with CERTH and at least one member must be specialized in Ethics or Bioethics. The knowledge background of the committee members should, as far as possible, reflects the disciplines and scopes of CERTH. The term of their duties lasts three (3) years and is renewable only once. The committee meets regularly once (1) a month and extraordinarily whenever requested by its Chairman, the Chairman of the Board of the research body. The compulsory documents concern (1) the approval of study conduct, (2) the consent and information procedures in respect to voluntary participation of humans in the study and (3) ethics protocol which initiates clear ethical guidelines and principles.

³ <https://www.kuleuven.be/english/research/ethics/committees/smec>

⁴ <https://www.kuleuven.be/english/research/ethics/committees/smec/documents-and-guidance-for-your-application>

The study was submitted on 14th March 2022 to The Ethical Committee of CERTH (Annex: Case 2 CERTH (Greece) Proof of ethics submission). The ethics board approved the study on 17th March 2022 (Annex: Case 2 CERTH (Greece) Proof of ethics approval).

4.4 Case Study 3: UX With Gradior Active for Physical Training Reinforcing Dual Task Performance

This small-scale pilot will be conducted by INTRAS (Spain). The aim of this case study is to test the Gradior Active prototype by assessing its usability, learnability, acceptance, and the overall experience of participants, especially in terms of how easy and pleasing it is to use or its perceived utility when embedded in active and healthy aging programs. Study focuses also on performing a cocreation sprint to understand the challenges for optimizing the program and its implementation in real settings and services (eg, exploring ideal workflows). In all, the case study aims to understand what is most important for the user experience perspective and for developing big data–driven hybrid personas through the initially described harmonized research protocol.

4.4.1 Ethical review process in Spain

The study with the pilot activity will be submitted to the ethics committee of the “Hospital Universitario Río Hortega”, Valladolid East Health Area Research Ethics Committee (CEIm)⁵. The co-creation activities will be accepted by the internal committee of Fundación INTRAS.

The documents required in the process includes (1) Protocol of the research project, (2) Financial report, (3) Patient information sheet and informed consent, (4) Request for evaluation of the research project, (5) Application letter, (6) Conformity of the head of service, (7) Certificate of suitability of the facilities, (8) Certificate of commitment of the research team, (9) Certificate of suitability of the investigating team, (10) Management's conformity.

The internal committee of Fundación INTRAS requires following documents: (1) Application letter and (2) Ethical protocol report of the study focusing on the co-creation activity.

The study was submitted on 24th January 2022 to The Ethical Committee of CEIm (Annex: Case 3 INTRAS (Spain) Proof of ethics submission). The ethics board concluded on 24th February 2022 during the face-to-face meeting that the study application should be resend being identified as “clinical trial” instead of “research study” and with the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products resolution on whether Gradior is considered as a medical device or not (new recently established procedure). The second application prepared but waiting feedback from the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products to proceed.

4.5 Cross-country case Study 4: Multidimensional Physical Fitness Testing Protocol for Aging Persons

This small-scale pilot will be conducted by Laurea (Finland), GAIA (Spain) and TREBAG (Hungary). This case study will develop and test a physical fitness testing protocol for older adults in real-life settings in 3 countries: Finland, Spain, and Hungary. The perceived user experience of the proposed comprehensive physical fitness level research protocol will be compared with a well-established but less comprehensive protocol. Furthermore, the pre- and post training period physical fitness levels will be compared in the cases of the Spain and Hungary case studies to provide suggestions on how to improve the training programs.

4.5.1 Ethical review process in Finland

The study with the pilot activity will be submitted to “The Human Sciences Ethics Committee of the Helsinki Region Universities of Applied Sciences”. As the name states, it is one committee for seven local University of Applied sciences. According to Finnish legislation of Medical research one must

⁵ <https://www.icscyl.com/hcuv/east-valladolid-area-ceim/>

apply an ethical statement the from Medical Ethical committee⁶, if the research is somehow concerning health issues, the target group is somehow impaired etc. If that would be the case then the ethical committee evaluation would be obtained from HUS (Helsinki University hospital).

The documents required in “The Human Sciences Ethics Committee of the Helsinki Region Universities of Applied Sciences⁷” process includes following documents: (1) Appendices to the request for a statement, (2) Research plan, (3) Data management plan (may be included in the research plan), (4) Information document for the research participants, (5) Consent form for the research participants, (6) Privacy notice, if a personal data register will be created in your research, (7) Other material to be given to the research participants (e.g. questionnaire, interview outline), (8) Possible recruitment notices to be given to the research participants and (9) Copy of an earlier statement (does not apply to new research).

The study was submitted on 8th February 2022 to The Ethical Committee of CERTH (Annex: Case 4.1 Laurea (Finland) Proof of ethics submission 1). On 22th February 2022 (received 4th March 2022), the ethics board provided conditional approval and requested a list of addition before issuing a final opinion (Annex: Case 4.1 Laurea (Finland) Proof of ethics approval). The study was re-submitted on 31th March 2022 to The Ethical Committee of CERTH (Annex: Case 4.1 Laurea (Finland) Proof of ethics submission 2).

4.5.2 Ethical review process in Spain

Tomas Iriondo, as General Manager and Coordinator at GAIA Cluster, is responsible for the internally established Ethical Committee at GAIA. Once a month Mr. Tomas Iriondo together with the cluster’s President are analyzing the submission and providing answers. The compulsory document includes Research Protocol. In a second phase (1) the “Informed Consent”, (2) “Participant Information Sheet” and (3) RGD Treatment Declaration Form for Investigation Purposes” will be needed.

The study was submitted on 28th January 2022 to Ethical Committee at GAIA (Annex: Case 4.2 GAIA (Spain) Proof of ethics submission). It is estimated that Ethical Committee decision will be made at the beginning of April.

4.5.3 Ethical review process in Hungary

The study with the pilot activity will be submitted to Research Ethics Committee of Eotvos University FFP, Budapest. The Research Ethics Committee⁸ (REC) can provide a research ethics permission only to those who are public servants (or employed as emeritus professor) of the ELTE FFP and have a scientific qualification (PhD, CSc, DSc). The documents required in The Research Ethics Committee process includes following documents (1) Ethical permission, (2) Permission for data processing and (3) Permission to data processing – Appendix.

The ethics application will be submitted on April to The Research Ethics Committee.

4.6 Cross-country Case Study 5: Characterizing the Interaction of the Effects of a Museum Visit on Mobility, Cognition, and Well-being in People With Stroke

This small-scale pilot will be conducted by McGill-UDEM (Canada) and AUTH (Greece). This small-scale pilot aims to obtain measurements of mobility, cognition, and well-being of people with stroke and healthy ageing individuals using innovative technologies to explore the lived experiences of these individuals as they participate in a museum environment. The collected data will be used to (1) study the feasibility of conducting a series of diverse measurements in a museum setting, (2)

⁶ <https://www.hus.fi/en/about-us/administration-and-decision-making/committees>

⁷ <https://www.metropolia.fi/en/rdi/ethics-committee>

⁸ <https://www.ppk.elte.hu/en/research-ethics-committee>

study the acceptability of such interventions in a museum setting, and (3) create a user model that can be adopted to describe people with disabilities visiting a museum in future big data collection.

4.6.1 Ethical review process in Canada

CRIR Research Ethics Board (REB)⁹ is designated by Quebec's Minister of Health and Social Services under Article 21 of the Civil Code of Quebec, allowing the REB to evaluate projects involving a minor or a person of full age who is incapable of giving consent. It is constructed in accordance with the "Regulations concerning the Creation and Operation of the Research Ethics Board for the CRIR Institutions" (Règlement portant sur la création et le fonctionnement du CÉR des établissements du CRIR). The "REB Internal Management Rules and Regulations" (Règles de régie interne) define the REB functioning modalities. The REB is recognized by the three universities affiliated with CRIR: McGill University, Université de Montréal and Université du Québec à Montréal. The committee meets approximately once per month to evaluate applications submitted. The 2021-2022 calendar is available online¹⁰.

Required documents include (1) Research protocol, (2) Consent form(s), (3) A copy of (or link to) all PROMs and PREMs used in the study, (4) there are various forms that must be completed on the Nagano platform, (5) Scientific evaluation (either from a funding agency or by the local scientific evaluation committee, if the study has not been funded). Optional documents include Recruitment procedure form (<https://crir.ca/en/ethics/documentation/>).

The case study 5 will be a part of the ongoing NEURO-MBAM-project which has received ethics approval in the 19th of October 2020 (Annex: Case 5.1 (McGill-UDEM) Proof of ethics approval) and therefore re-submission is not needed.

4.6.2 Ethical review process in Greece

The Committee on Research Ethics and Conduct of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EHDE AUTH), or Ethics Committee RC AUTH¹¹ as it is usually called, was established in accordance with law N. 4521/2018 of the Greek government (articles 21-27 Chapter 5 – Committees on Research Ethics and Conduct) in 2018. It falls under the umbrella of the Research Committee of AUTH and is comprised of five (5) permanent members of staff of AUTH and two (2) external associates. There is no specific schedule that applicants need to abide by to submit the applications. Pursuant to article 23 par. 4 of law 4521/2018 the Ethics Committee RC AUTH should discuss the requests and reach a decision or request additional information within a reasonable time that cannot exceed fifteen (15) days from the submission of the application and all accompanying documents. If the 15 day period passes and the committee hasn't replied, the application is considered approved.

Required documents include (1) Application form signed by the scientific coordinator, (2) Research protocol, (3) Declaration of legal and ethical compliance signed by the scientific coordinator, (4) Ethics self-assessment Questionnaire, (5) Participant's informed consent form (if required) accompanied by the information form and other information material that will be given to the participants before obtaining their consent, (6) Required approval(s) from other competent authorities (e.g. of another institution) (if required).

The study was submitted on 17th March 2022 to The Ethical Committee of AUTH (Annex: Case 5 CERTH (Greece) Proof of ethics submission). The ethics board approved the study on 28th March 2022 (Annex: Case 5 AUTH (Greece) Proof of ethics approval).

⁹ <https://crir.ca/en/ethics/the-research-ethics-board-reb-in-brief/>

¹⁰ <https://crir.ca/en/ethics/submit-a-project/>

¹¹ <https://www.rc.auth.gr/ed/>

5 Conclusion

This document provided an overview of procedures and submissions in relation to ethics approval application in pilot case studies in WP7. The main output of this document is the current status analysis of the Ethical application approval process for JRA3. Table 1 provides the submission and approval status summary for all case studies.

Table 1 Submission and approval status summary for all case studies

Case study	Submission date	Approval status and date
Case 1.1: AIT (Austria)	12 th January 2022	According ethics board, study is not under Medical Devices Act. (19 th January 2022). Ethical approval is not needed, but reference was made to other regulations such as the Declaration of Helsinki, publication guidelines that should be followed.
Case 1.2: LiCalab	30 th November 2021	Approved (12 th December 2021)
Case 2: CERTH (Greece)	14 th March 2022	Approved (17 th March 2022)
Case 3: INTRAS (Spain)	<i>Submission 1</i> 24 th January 2022 <i>Submission 2</i> The second application is prepared but waiting for the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products resolution on whether Grador is considered as a medical device or not.	Re-submission request as “clinical trial” study received on 24 th February.
Case 4.1 Laurea (Finland)	<i>Submission 1</i> 8 th February 2022 <i>Submission 2</i> 31 st March	Conditional approval, addition information needed before issuing a final opinion (22 th February 2022).
Case 4.2 GAIA (Spain)	28 th January 2022	Decision is expected to come on April.
Case 4.3 TREBAG (Hungary)	Will be submitted on April	
Case 5.1 McGill-UDEM (Canada)	Done in a previous project.	A part of ongoing NEURO-MBAM-project, which has received ethics approval (19 th of October 2020). Re-submission is not needed.
Case 5.1 AUTH (Greece)	17 th March 2022	Approved (28 th March 2022)

The results indicate significant process time differences between the countries ranging from few days to over two months. This is important finding when defining harmonized living lab procedures. All but one VITALISE partner have submitted their ethical application. The missing partner (TREBAG) is submitting their application on April. Case studies 1, 2, and 5 have received approval

status. There are two re-submission requests. Case study 4.1 has made re-submission and case study 3 is planning to re-submit on April. Case study 4.2 is waiting a decision. As a summary, it is concluded that WP7 is progressing somewhat as planned, since additional information request are normal during the ethics process and the requested amendments where addressing on practical issues. The risk of delays that will have an impact on VITALISE project are not in sight.

The ethics application process description that were collected will later on serve as input for WP2 in order to understand the commonalities and differences of ethical procedure and to define common templates and procedures that can facilitate the ethics process in Living Labs. The results indicate that the decision process varies between the countries. Most commonly there is an ethical board who makes a decision during the board meeting after having a discussion. In one case (CERTH) an email process where review board members individually signed the documents were executed instead having a board meeting. Three different types of the boards were identified: Internal entities, external and mixed entities. Internal entity refers to ethical board operating within the organization who is conducting the study, whereas external refers to board not directly associated with the organization conducting the study. Mixed board includes both external and internal actors and can be managed by the research organization or external entity.

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex: Case 1.1 AIT (Austria)

Proof of ethics submission

From: Neureiter Katja <Katja.Neureiter@ait.ac.at>
Sent: keskiviikko 12. tammikuuta 2022 15.59
To: ethikkommission@ma15.wien.gv.at
Cc: Garschall Markus
Subject: Evaluierungsstudie im Rahmen des H2020 Projekts VITALISE
Attachments: Studiendesign_ethical application.pdf; Vitalise_Einwilligungserklärung_JRA.pdf

Sehr geehrter Herr Undeutsch,

Im Rahmen des EU Projekts Vitalise (Programm H2020 „Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure“) ist das AIT, Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH, für die Planung, Durchführung und Auswertung einer Feldstudie verantwortlich, bei der eine Coaching App von potentiellen Endanwender*innen über einen Zeitraum von 8 Wochen getestet wird (geplanter Studienstart ist April 2022). Personalisierte Vorschläge sollen die Nutzer*innen zur Verhaltensänderung motivieren. Verschiedene Aspekte wie beispielsweise physisches, psychisches aber auch mentales und soziales Wohlbefinden werden dabei adressiert.

Für diese Studie bitten wir Sie um eine schriftliche Stellungnahme hinsichtlich der Notwendigkeit einer Einreichung bei der Ethikkommission der Stadt Wien.

Im Anhang übermittle ich Ihnen das Studiendesign mit einer detaillierten Beschreibung zu Zielen, Ablauf, und Datenverwertung. Weiters ist auch die Einverständniserklärung zu Teilnahme an der Studie angehängt.

Für Rückfragen stehe ich gerne zur Verfügung.
Ich freue mich über eine Rückmeldung!

Mit freundlichen Grüßen
Katja Neureiter

KATJA NEUREITER
Scientist
Center for Technology Experience

AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Giefinggasse 2 | 1210 Vienna | Austria
T +43 50550-4535 | M +43 664 8251402
katja.neureiter@ait.ac.at | <http://www.ait.ac.at>

FN: 115980 i HG Wien | UID: ATU14703506
<http://www.ait.ac.at/Email-Disclaimer>

Proof of ethics approval

Ethikkommission der Stadt Wien
Thomas-Klestil-Platz 8,
Town Town, 1. Stock, CB 12.103
A-1030 Wien
Zugang: Schnirchgasse 12,
Stiege 2, CB 12.103
A-1030 Wien
Tel.: +43 1 4000-87754
Fax: +43 1 4000-99-87754
ethikkommission@m15.magwien.gv.at
www.gesundheitsdienst.wien.at

MA 15 – EK/22-018-VK_NZ

Wien, 19. Jänner 2022

Frau Katja Neureiter
AIT GmbH
per E-Mail

Sehr geehrte Frau Neureiter!

Anlässlich Ihres Ansuchens zur Beurteilung der Studie mit dem Titel:

„Programm H2020 Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure (VITALISE)“
“Evaluation of the digital coaching app ProSelf”

vom 12. Jänner 2022 teilen wir Ihnen mit, dass vorbehaltlich es sich nicht um eine Studie nach dem Medizinproduktegesetz handelt, eine gesetzlich vorgeschriebene Verpflichtung zur Beurteilung eines Forschungsprojekts durch die Ethikkommission der Stadt Wien für die Prüfung von Arzneimitteln oder Medizinprodukten oder die Anwendung neuer medizinischer Methoden am Menschen nicht besteht. Keines der genannten Kriterien trifft auf das gegenständliche Projekt zu, sodass eine Zuständigkeit unserer Ethikkommission gemäß Arzneimittelgesetz, Medizinproduktegesetz und Wiener Krankenanstaltengesetz nicht gegeben ist.

Verkehrsverbindung: U3 – U-Bahn Station Erdberg, Ausgang Nottendorfer Gasse bzw. U-Bahn Station Schlachthausgasse Ausgang Markthofgasse
Straßenbahnlinie 18, Station Schlachthausgasse und lokale Bus-Linien

6.2 Annex: Case 1.2 LiCalab (Belgium)

Submission notification

From: Sylvie Bernaerts <sylvie.bernaerts@thomasmore.be>

Sent: dinsdag 30 november 2021 18:19

To: SMEC <smec@kuleuven.be>

Cc: Nele De Witte <nele.dewitte1@thomasmore.be>; Vicky Van der Auwera <vicky.vanderauwera@thomasmore.be>; Leen Broeckx <leen.broeckx@thomasmore.be>

Subject: Aanvraag tot goedkeuring studieprotocol

Geachte leden van de ethische commissie,

In bijlage kan u de nodige documenten vinden ter goedkeuring.
Indien u bijkomende vragen heeft, dan horen we het graag.

Alvast bedankt!

Sylvie

Thomas More

Health & Care Challenges

Campus Sanderus | Molenstraat 8 | BE-2018 Antwerpen

T. + 32 (0)34 32 40 50 | www.e-mentalhealth.be | www.thomasmore.be

Blijf op de hoogte van al ons onderzoeksnieuws

via Facebook, LinkedIn en Twitter!

Proof of ethics approval

From: [SMEC](#)
To: [Sylvie Bernaerts](#)
Cc: [Nele De Witte](#); [Vicky Van der Auwera](#); [Leen Broeckx](#)
Subject: RE: Aanvraag tot goedkeuring studieprotocol
Date: tiistai 14. joulukuuta 2021 15.11.48
Attachments: [image001.jpg](#)

Beste Onderzoeker,

Uw onderzoeksproject "Virtual coaching to support a healthy and meaningful life of older adults and employees in their retirement process" werd gereviewd door de SMEC raad.

De raad concludeerde dat uw protocol voldoet aan de gestelde ethische normen met betrekking tot wetenschappelijk onderzoek.

Haar beslissing met betrekking tot dit protocol is daarom: **Gunstig**.

Uw protocol kreeg het volgende finale dossiernummer:

G-2021 12 2092

Gelieve het G-nummer te vermelden bij verdere communicatie, dus bewaar deze e-mail goed. Deze goedkeuring is 4 jaar geldig.

SMEC beschouwt uw dossier bij deze als afgehandeld. Indien u bijkomende vragen heeft kan u ons steeds contacteren.

Vriendelijke groeten,
Laurens Vangeel
Namens SMEC review board

<https://www.kuleuven.be/english/research/ethics/committees/smec>

6.3 Annex: Case 2: CERTH (Greece)

Proof of ethics submission

Submitted to: Ethical Committee
of CERTH

Ref. No: ETH.COM-71
Date Submitted: 14/03/2022
Review Completed:
Researcher(s) Notified:

**Application for Ethical Approval from
CERTH Research Ethics Panel**

Name of researcher: *Konstantinos Votis* Email: *kvotis@iti.gr*

Project Title: "Virtual health And wellBeing Living Lab InfraStructurE (VITALIZE)"

Dear members of CERTH's Ethics committee,

In the context of VITALIZE project, coordinated by ENoLL, CERTH aims to use nZEB Smart Home services as a controlled lab environment to guide real life case studies of older adults' concerns healthy ageing and place emphasis on social care addressing the interests of older-old adults. More specifically the main aims of the study are to understand and meet older adults' needs and preferences in order to provide proper services, systems and policies for non-pharmaceutical interventions based on cognitive and physical exercise training.

Aligned with LLs innovation and research benefits, CERTH/ITI developed the nZEB Smart Home as a rapid prototyping and novel technologies' demonstration infrastructure resembling a real domestic building. In the context of the VITALIZE project, in this fully operational smart home infrastructure, participants will experience training to reach better cognitive and physical health. One of the main purposes of the current study is to utilise a multi-component intervention, built upon a range of technologies, such as sensors for physiological monitoring, cognitive virtual games (e.g., virtual reality brain training games for MCI detection), and a virtual coach for physical activity promotion.

More specifically, mental, and physical exercises, such as cognitive games and physical fitness programs in the form of "yoga" along with stretching exercises and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) relaxation and mindfulness techniques, adjustable to user fitness level and preferences are planned to be included in the present study. The main goal of the present study is to evaluate nZEB Smart Home services and technologies assessing their usability and acceptance by healthy aging target groups.

Considering the foreseen pilots with human participants, it is considered important that CERTH ethics committee would provide their ethics opinion on nZEB Smart Home pilots. In this respect, we would like to inquire whether CERTH's Ethics committee is willing to undertake this role, during the planning and execution of nZEB Smart Home pilots. The relevant study design, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data clusters and treatment can be found in the enclosed Appendix.

I have read the institutes policies regarding their involvement of human participants and agree to abide by them. I am also familiar with the ethical principles about human participants and the Data Protection Act. I further agree to submit any significant changes in procedures or measurement instruments (as presented in Appendix) for additional review.

Signed:

Researcher

Konstantinos Votis
Konstantinos Votis

Ethical Committee Members

Χριστίνα Καραμανίδου
Χριστίνα Καραμανίδου

Συμεών Παπαδόπουλος
Συμεών Παπαδόπουλος

Ελένη Παπαϊωάννου
Ελένη Παπαϊωάννου

Κατερίνα Τούλιου
Κατερίνα Τούλιου

Κατερίνα Βαξεβάνη
Κατερίνα Βαξεβάνη

Proof of ethics approval

Subject:RE: Application for Ethical Approval from CERTH Research Ethics Panel
Date:Thu, 31 Mar 2022 15:36:19 +0300
From:Fotini Kopani <kopani@certh.gr>
To:'Sofia Segkouli' <ssofia@iti.gr>, 'Konstantinos Votis' <kvotis@iti.gr>

Dear Mrs. Segkouli

Attached please find the pdf document concerning the ethical approval of VITALISE.
In the document is clearly shown the date of submission and the date of completion of the procedure.
The document has been submitted on 14th of March and the last member of the Committee has signed on 17th of March.

Please let me know if this is sufficient.

Fotini Kopani
Finances and Administration Head
Institute of Applied Bioscience
Centre for Research and Technology - Hellas
6th km Charilaou - Thermi Rd.
P.O.Box 60361
GR-57001 Thermi, Thessaloniki
Hellas
Tel. +302310498272
Fax +302310498270
email: kopani@certh.gr, <http://www.inab.certh.gr>

Ref. No: ETH.COM-71

Submitted to: Ethical Committee
of CERTH

Date Submitted: 14/03/2022

Review Completed: 17/03/2022

Researcher(s) Notified:

**Application for Ethical Approval from
CERTH Research Ethics Panel**

Name of researcher: *Konstantinos Votis*

Email: *kvotis@iti.gr*

Project Title: "Virtual health And wellbeing Living Lab InfraStructure (VITALIZE)"

Dear members of CERTH's Ethics committee,

In the context of VITALIZE project, coordinated by ENOLL, CERTH aims to use nZEB Smart Home services as a controlled lab environment to guide real life case studies of **older adults' concerns healthy ageing and place emphasis on social care addressing the interests** of older-old adults. More specifically the main aims of the study are to understand and meet **older adults' needs and preferences in order to provide proper services, systems and policies** for non-pharmaceutical interventions based on cognitive and physical exercise training.

Aligned with LLs innovation and research benefits, CERTH/ITI developed the nZEB Smart Home as a **rapid prototyping and novel technologies' demonstration infrastructure** resembling a real domestic building. In the context of the VITALIZE project, in this fully operational smart home infrastructure, participants will experience training to reach better cognitive and physical health. One of the main purposes of the current study is to utilise a multi-component intervention, built upon a range of technologies, such as sensors for physiological monitoring, cognitive virtual games (e.g., virtual reality brain training games for MCI detection), and a virtual coach for physical activity promotion.

More specifically, mental, and physical exercises, such as cognitive games and physical fitness programs **in the form of "yoga" along with stretching exercises and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) relaxation and mindfulness techniques**, adjustable to user fitness level and preferences are planned to be included in the present study. The main goal of the present study is to evaluate nZEB Smart Home services and technologies assessing their usability and acceptance by healthy aging target groups.

Considering the foreseen pilots with human participants, it is considered important that CERTH ethics committee would provide their ethics opinion on nZEB Smart Home pilots. In this respect, we would like to inquire whether **CERTH's Ethics committee is willing to undertake this role**, during the planning and execution of nZEB Smart Home pilots. The

1

relevant study design, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data clusters and treatment can be found in the enclosed Appendix.

I have read the institutes policies regarding their involvement of human participants and agree to abide by them. I am also familiar with the ethical principles about human participants and the Data Protection Act. I further agree to submit any significant changes in procedures or measurement instruments (as presented in Appendix) for additional review.

Signed:

Researcher

Konstantinos Votis

Ethical Committee Members

Χριστίνα Καραμανίδου

Συμεών Παπαδόπουλος

Ελένη Παπαϊωάννου

Κατερίνα Τούλιου

Κατερίνα Βαξεβάνη

6.4 Annex: Case 3: INTRAS (Spain)

Proof of ethics submission

Sofía Ballesteros Rodríguez

De: Alvarez González, Javier <jalvarezgo@saludcastillayleon.es>
Enviado el: miércoles, 26 de enero de 2022 8:24
Para: Sofía Ballesteros Rodríguez; F. Javier Alvarez
CC: Raquel Losada Durán; Rosa Almeida
Asunto: RE: Solicitud de aprobación por parte del Comité Ético

Hola de nuevo

Hemos recibido la documentación del proyecto.

PI 22-2570 NO HCUV	VITALISE-VIRTUAL HEALTH AND WELLBEING LIVING LAB INFRASTRUCTURE. ESTUDIO EXPERIMENTAL "EXPERIENCIA DEL USUARIO CON GRADIOR ACTIVE PARA EL ENTRENAMIENTO FÍSICO Y COGNITIVO DUAL TASK	H2020-EU.1.4.1.2-INTEGRATING AND OPENING EXISTING NATIONAL AND REGIONAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES OF EUROPEAN INTEREST. ACUERDO DE SUBVENCIÓN: 101007990 I.P.: RAQUEL LOSADA EQUIPO: YOLANDA BUENO, ROSA ALMEIDA, SOFIA BALLESTEROS FUNDACIÓN INTRAS
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Un saludo

Prof. F. Javier Álvarez
 CEIm Área de Salud Valladolid Este,
 Hospital Clínico Universitario de Valladolid,
 Farmacología,
 Facultad de Medicina,
 Universidad de Valladolid, C/ Ramón y Cajal 7,
 47005 Valladolid
alvarez@med.uva.es, jalvarezgo@saludcastillayleon.es
<https://www.icscyl.com/hcuv/ceimvalladolideste/>
 tel: 983 423077 y 682926258 (de 13:00h a 14:00h)
 fax: 983 423022

De: Sofía Ballesteros Rodríguez <sofiabr@intras.es>
Enviado: lunes, 24 de enero de 2022 09:58
Para: F. Javier Alvarez <alvarez@med.uva.es>; Alvarez González, Javier <jalvarezgo@saludcastillayleon.es>
Cc: Raquel Losada Durán <rlid@intras.es>; Rosa Almeida <rra@intras.es>
Asunto: Solicitud de aprobación por parte del Comité Ético

Estimado Comité Ético CEIm Área de Salud Valladolid Este,

Contactamos desde Fundación INTRAS para solicitar aprobación ética para el Estudio Experimental "Experiencia del usuario con Grador Active para el entrenamiento físico y cognitivo Dual Task" en una muestra de personas mayores con dificultad en el movimiento. Se trata de un estudio a desarrollar en el marco del Proyecto VITALISE financiado por el programa H2020-EU.1.4.1.2- Integrating and opening existing national and regional research infrastructures of European interest.

Adjuntamos los siguientes documentos:

- Solicitud de evaluación.
- Carta al comité ético
- Protocolo: Estudio Experimental "Experiencia del usuario con Grador Active para el entrenamiento físico y cognitivo Dual Task"
 - Memoria del Proyecto de Investigación.
 - Memoria Económica (anexo a la memoria del proyecto).
 - Certificados: de idoneidad de las instalaciones; de idoneidad del equipo investigador; de compromiso del equipo investigador; conformidad de la Gerencia de Fundación INTRAS; Conformidad del Jefe de servicio;(anexos a la memoria del proyecto).
- Curriculum de investigador principal.

Esperando su respuesta, les saluda atentamente,

Sofía Ballesteros Rodríguez

Trabajadora Social, Fundación INTRAS.

6.5 Annex: Case 4.1 Laurea (Finland)

Proof of ethics submission 1

Lähettäjä: Funet FileSender <filesender@funet.fi>
Lähetetty: tiistai 8. helmikuuta 2022 20.46
Vastaanottaja: Mikko Julin <Mikko.Julin@laurea.fi>
Aihe: Funet FileSender: Files available for download

Hello,

The following files have been uploaded to [Funet FileSender](#) by Mikko.Julin@laurea.fi and you have been granted permission to download their contents.

Transaction details	
Files	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Vitalise eng lausuntopyyntomake.pdf (1 MB)• JMIR Cocreating a Harmonized Living Lab for Big Data Driven Hybrid.pdf (313.3 kB)
Transfer size	1.3 MB
Expiry date	22/02/2022
Download link	https://filesender.funet.fi/?s=download&token=21c5bec8-7fc0-4e87-8217-f88ac813da90

Personal message from Mikko.Julin@laurea.fi:

Hei,pyytäisimme lausunnon englanniksi, koska kyseessä on osa H2020 rahoitteista hanketta. Lisäksi olemme julkaiseet tutkimussuunnitelman vertaisarvioidussa lehdessä. Laitoin pyyntöomakkeeseen hyperlinkin sinne, mutta varmuuden vuoksi laitoin sen toisena liitteenä mukaan.

Best regards,
Funet FileSender

Translate this email: https://filesender.funet.fi/?s=translate_email&token=b4d6e46d-3336-4d17-a71d-fe8ece0d3de2

Proof of ethics submission 2

Lähetäjä: Funet FileSender <filesender@funet.fi>
Lähetetty: torstai 31. maaliskuuta 2022 15.15
Vastaanottaja: Mikko Julin <Mikko.Julin@laurea.fi>
Aihe: Funet FileSender: Vitalise 5/2022 täydennys

Hello,

The following file has been uploaded to [Funet FileSender](#) by Mikko.Julin@laurea.fi and you have been granted permission to download its contents.

Transaction details	
File	Vitalise lausuntopyyntö 5_22 täydennytyt liitteet.pdf (6.6 MB)
Expiry date	06/04/2022
Download link	https://filesender.funet.fi/?s=download&token=bc122d2c-c0e2-468f-a8b3-f721a284a5f9

Personal message from Mikko.Julin@laurea.fi:

Hei,

Ohessa Vitalise Lausuntopyyntö 5/2022 pyydetyt täydennykset.

Best regards,
Funet FileSender

Translate this email: https://filesender.funet.fi/?s=translate_email&token=224e1851-8e88-4957-93a3-319ab772e3e5

Proof of ethics approval

Pääkaupunkiseudun ammattikorkeakoulujen ihmistieteiden eettinen toimikunta

Lausuntopyyntö 5/2022

Tutkimuksen nimi: Cocreating a harmonized Living Lab for Big Data–driven hybrid persona development: Protocol for cocreating, testing, and seeking consensus

Vastaava tutkija: Mikko Julin, Laurea

Lausuntopyynnön käsittely

Pääkaupunkiseudun ammattikorkeakoulujen ihmistieteiden eettinen toimikunta käsitteli lausuntopyyntöänne kokouksessaan 22.2.2022. Eettistä ennakkoarviota haetaan, koska tutkimuksessa puututaan tutkittavien fyysiseen koskemattomuuteen.

Toimikunnan kommentit

Yleisesti:

- TENK:n ohjeen (TENK 2019: Ihmiseen kohdistuvan tutkimuksen eettiset periaatteet ja ihmistieteiden eettinen ennakkoarviointi Suomessa) mukaan ”eettisellä ennakkoarvioinnilla tarkoitetaan suunnitteilla olevan tutkimuksen sellaista arvioimista, jossa painotetaan tutkimuksesta tai sen tuloksista tutkittavalle henkilölle mahdollisesti koituvan haitan ennakoimista. Myös tutkittavien informointiin ja suostumuksiin laaditut dokumentit tarkastetaan”.
- Lausuntopyynnön mukana toimitetun tutkimussuunnitelman mukaan tutkittavina ovat ikääntyneet kansalaiset, jotka osallistuvat fyysisen toimintakyvyn mittauksiin. Lisäksi 20 toimintakykymittauksiin osallistunutta senioria osallistuu fyysisen aktiivisuuden mittauksiin pitämällä vuorokauden aktiivisuusranneketta. Tutkimussuunnitelman mukaan toimintakykymittauksiin pyritään rekrytoimaan myös aiempaa ”huonompikuntoisia” henkilöitä.

Yksittäiset kommentit

- Toimikunnalle toimitetusta materiaalista puuttuvat tutkittaville menevät ohjeet siitä, miten osallistujat valmistautuvat testeihin.
- Materiaalista puuttuu maininta, mitkä ovat testeihin osallistumisen mahdolliset vasta-aiheet (poissulkukriteerit) ja miten osallistumiskelpoisuus varmistetaan.
- Tutkimussuunnitelmassa on kuvattava tutkittavien rekrytointi Elä ja Asu -seniorikeskuksista, lisättävä kuvaus siellä tehtävistä toimintakykymittauksista ja liitettävä mukaan tutkittaville menevä materiaali.
- Tiedote tutkimuksesta (toimintakykymittaukset yhteistyössä Espoon kaupungin liikuntatoimi)
 - o Luettuaan tiedotteen tutkittava ymmärtää, mitä *tutkittavana oleminen* hänen kannaltaan tarkoittaa. Tiedotteen mukaan ”tutkimus toteutetaan siten, että osallistujia pyydetään aluksi täyttämään pari kyselylomaketta. Sen jälkeen mittauksiin osallistutaan normaalin kaavan mukaan”. Se, mihin tutkittavaa pyydetään osallistumaan tutkimustarkoituksessa, on kuvattava nykyistä tarkemmin asiatyylillä.
 - o Kohta ”toimintakykymittauksen protokollaa” on muutettava niin, että kohderyhmä sen ymmärtää.
 - o Kohta ”toimintakykymittauksia suorittamaan”. Tutkittavat eivät suorita toimintakykymittauksia, vaan osallistuvat niihin - muutettava.
 - o Kohta ”Kieltäytyminen ei vaikuta mitenkään mahdollisuuteen osallistua mittaustapahtumaan ilman, että annatte tuloksianne tutkimuksen käyttöön” on vaikeasti ymmärrettävä ja kohdan voi muuttaa muotoon ”Voitte osallistua normaalisti toimintakykymittauksiin, vaikkette osallistuisikaan tutkimukseen”.
 - o Suostumuksessa viitataan, että testeihin osallistumisen riskit kerrotaan tiedotteessa. Arvio riskeistä on lisättävä testeistä kertovaan tiedotteeseen.
 - o Tiedotteesta kannattaa poistaa tarpeettomat tekstikohdat, kuten ”Mittaustulokset kirjataan yhdelle paperille kahteen kertaan joka pisteellä”.
 - o Kohdan ”Henkilötietoja ei kerätä, vaan tuloslomakkeet numeroidaan tallentamisen helpottamiseksi. Näin ollen yksittäistä osallistujaa on mahdotonta tunnistaa. Tuloksissa ei myöskään olla kiinnostuneita yksittäisen osallistujien tuloksista, vaan kaikki tulokset käsitellään ja julkaistaan ryhmätuloksina” voi yksinkertaisesti esittää muodossa ”Tutkimustieto kerätään, tutkimustulokset analysoidaan ja raportoidaan niin, ettei yksittäistä tutkittavaa voi tunnistaa”.

D7.2 Ethical application documents for JRA3

- Suostumus (toimintakykymittaukset yhteistyössä Espoon kaupungin liikuntatoimi)
 - o Tutkittavan tiedotteen mukaan tutkimuksessa ei kerätä henkilötietoja, mutta tutkittavat allekirjoittavat tutkimukseen suostumuksensa. Mikäli suostumuksella tarkoitetaan ”eettistä” suostumusta osallistua tutkimukseen, osallistujalistan keräämisen (nimi on henkilötieto) voi perustella tietosuojalomakkeen kohdassa ”Henkilötietojenne käsittelyn tarkoitus”. Tässä voi esimerkiksi kertoa, että allekirjoituksella varmennetaan, että tutkittava on tutustunut tutkimuksen tiedotteeseen ja täyttänyt esitietolomakkeet.
 - o Tutkittavan suostumuslomakkeessa ei pyydetä erikseen suostumusta henkilötietojen käsittelyyn. Toimikunta kuitenkin tulkitsee, että nykymuodossaan suostumus tarkoittaa suostumusta osallistua tutkimukseen ja myös suostumusta henkilötietojen käsittelyyn. Suostumuslomakkeen kohta ”Olen tietoinen siitä, että mikäli keskeytän tutkimuksen tai peruutan suostumuksen, minusta keskeyttämiseen ja suostumuksen peruuttamiseen mennessä kerättyjä tietoja ja näytteitä voidaan käyttää osana tutkimusaineistoa” viittaa siihen, että tutkittava voi käyttää oikeuttaan poistattaa tietonsa. Kun suostumus pyydetään erikseen niin, ettei sitä voi yhdistää tutkittavan mittausdataan, tutkittava ei voi käyttää em. oikeuttaan. Suostumusasiakirjasta on poistettava tarpeettomat vakiotekstit ja se on räätälöitävä kyseiseen tutkimukseen tutkimuseettisiä periaatteita ja tietosuojasäädöksiä noudattaen.
- Tiedote tutkimuksesta (aktiivisuusmittari)
 - o Kohderyhmä huomioiden tiedotteessa voi olla maininta, mitä tutkittava tekee, jos laite rikkoutuu tai se häviää.
 - o Tämän tutkimusvaiheen henkilötietoja ovat tietosuojaselosteen mukaan suostumus (nimi) ja yhteystiedot. Toimikunnassa keskusteltiin aktiivisuusrannekkeeseen tallentuvasta mittaustiedosta, josta on maininta tiedotteessa. Mikäli mittaustieto tallentuu vain rannekkeeseen ja josta se siirretään tietokoneelle ilman tunnistetietoja, niin tämä on syytä mainita lyhyesti tiedotteessa. Jos mittaustiedon tallentaminen ja analysoiminen edellyttää tunnistetietoja, niin tiedotteessa (+ tietosuojaseloste) on kuvattava henkilötietojen käsittely ja niiden käsittelyyn on oltava peruste (tutkittavan suostumus).
 - o Toimikunnalle jää epäselväksi, miten aktiivisuusrannekkeen mittaustieto yhdistetään päiväkirjatietoon ilman tunnistetietoja. Kuvattava, miten käytännössä menetellään.
 - o Tiedotteen mukaan ”Mittarin tulokset kerrotaan ja jaetaan osallistujalle joko elektronisena tai printtinä toimitettuna”. Tiedotteen lukeneelle jää epäselväksi, miten hänestä kerätään ilman tunnistetietoja mittaustietoa, se yhdistetään päiväkirjatietoon ja lopulta hänelle toimitetaan palaute. Toimintapa on kuvattava lyhyesti tiedotteessa.
 - o Tiedotteesta on poistettava epäoleelliset kohdat, kuten ”Tutkimusten mukaan mittari on kohtuullisen tarkka”.
 - o Tiedotteen mukaan ”Raportti on myös yksityiskohtainen koko vuorokauden ajalta”. Kohta ei ole tutkittavalle informatiivinen ja niiden tutkittavien osalta, jotka mittausaikana harrastavat uintia tai muuta vesiliikuntaa, mittaus aliarvioi fyysisen aktiivisuuden määrää. Tämä mittausmenetelmän rajoite on kerrottava tutkittaville fyysisestä aktiivisuudesta raportoitaessa.
 - o Tutkijoiden yhteystiedot; lisättävä tutkijoiden koulutus.
- Suostumus (aktiivisuusmittari)
 - o Mittaritutkimuksesta ei ole erillistä suostumusasiakirjaa. Laadittava.
- Toimikunta suosittaa, että tehtyjen korjausten jälkeen tutkittavalle jaettava materiaali tarkastetaan kielen osalta.

Ennakoarviointilausunto

Eettisessä ennakoarvioinnissa tarkastellaan aineistonkeruun suunnitelmaa ja tutkimuksen suunniteltua toteutustapaa riskien ja vahingon välttämisen näkökulmasta. Toimikunta tekee päätöksensä sille toimitetun materiaalin perusteella. Lausunnoissaan toimikunta ei ota yksityiskohtaisesti kantaa tutkimuksen tieteelliseen arvoon ja validiteettiin, ei tutkittavien valintaan ja tutkimusmenetelmiin, eikä tutkimuksen toteutukseen ja tulosten julkaisemiseen. Ennakoarviointi ei siirrä vastuuta tutkimuksen eettisyydestä eettiselle toimikunnalle, vaan tutkija vastaa aina itse tutkimuksensa eettisistä ja moraalisisista ratkaisuista.

Toimikunta antaa tutkimukselle **myönteisen lausunnon ehdollisena**. Toimikunta pyytää edellä esitettyjä täydennyksiä ennen lopullisen lausunnon antamista. Lisäselvitykset pyydetään palauttamaan yhtenä PDF-tiedostona [Funet File Senderin](#) avulla. Vastanottajaksi merkitään toimikunnan sähköpostiosoite: eettinentoimikunta@arcada.fi. Tehdyt korjaukset tulee näkyä liitteissä joko yliviivauksin tai korostusmerkinnöin.

Jos tutkija ei noudata saamansa lausunnon ohjeistusta, kyseessä voi olla hyvän tieteellisen käytännön (HTK)-loukkaus. Mikäli ennakoarviointilausunnon pyytäjä ei hyväksy eettisen toimikunnan päätöstä, hän voi pyytää asiasta lausuntoa Tutkimuseettiseltä neuvottelukunnalta. Perusteltu lausuntopyyntö liitteineen on jätettävä kahden kuukauden kuluessa eettisen toimikunnan päätöksestä. Lisätietoja www.tenk.fi.

Helsingissä 3.3.2022

Jyrki Kettunen

Toimikunnan puheenjohtaja

6.6 Annex: Case 4.2 GAIA (Spain)

Proof of ethics submission

De: Idoia Muñoz
Enviado el: viernes, 28 de enero de 2022 14:33
Para: iriondo@gaia.es
CC: garatea@gaia.es
Asunto: Protocolo de Investigación para Comité de Ética - Pilotos VITALISE Project

1. Protocolo de Investigacion_VITALISE JRA1 & JRA3_Comite Etica.doc
140 KB

Hola Tomás,

En el marco del proyecto VITALISE - "Virtual health And wellbeing Living Lab InfraStructurE", tenemos que desplegar dos pilotos a pequeña escala en el marco de nuestros living labs para armonizar protocolos comunes de actuación entre living labs de Europa y Canadá. El primero de ellos será para testeo de tecnologías y metodologías creativas (musicoterapia/ arte terapia) para rehabilitación en situación de estrés en personas mayores, y el segundo de ellos se trata de un testeo conjunto con Finlandia y Hungría en torno a tecnologías y metodologías para testeo y mejora de la condición física en personas mayores. Como responsable del comité de ética de GAIA, adjunto el Protocolo de Investigación para ambos pilotos, conforme a los procedimientos internos establecidos.

Quedamos a la espera de vuestros comentarios.

Un saludo,
Idoia

6.7 Annex: Case 5.1 MCGILL-UdeM (Canada)

Proof of ethics approval

Comité d'éthique de la recherche
des établissements du CRIR

Montréal, le 19 octobre 2020

PAR COURRIER ÉLECTRONIQUE

Membres institutionnels :

- CISSS de Laval**
 - Hôpital juif de réadaptation
- CISSS de la Montérégie-Centre**
 - Institut Nazareth et Louis-Braille
- CIUSSS du Centre-Sud-de-l'Île-de-Montréal**
 - Institut universitaire sur la réadaptation en déficience physique de Montréal (IURDPM)
 - ▶ Pavillon Gingras
 - ▶ Pavillon Laurier
 - ▶ Pavillon Lindsay
- CIUSSS du Centre-Ouest-de-l'Île-de-Montréal**
 - Centre de réadaptation Lethbridge-Layton-Mackay
 - ▶ Site Constance-Lethbridge
 - ▶ Site MAB-Mackay

Membres partenaires :

- CISSS de Lanaudière**
 - Centre de réadaptation en déficience physique Le Bouclier
- CISSS des Laurentides**
 - Centre de réadaptation en déficience physique Le Bouclier

Madame Elaine de Guise Ph.D.
Professeure-adjointe
Université de Montréal (Campus Laval)
1700, rue Jacques-Tétreault, bureau 6230
Laval, QC, H7N 0B6

OBJET : Demande d'évaluation éthique du projet CRIR-1486-0320, intitulé «PROJET NEURO-MBAM : Caractérisation de l'interaction des effets d'une visite muséale sur la mobilité, la cognition et le bien-être des personnes avec une lésion cérébrale acquise ou une maladie neurodégénérative»

Madame,

Le Comité d'éthique de la recherche des établissements du CRIR (CÉR) tient d'abord à vous remercier de lui avoir présenté le projet de recherche précité à sa réunion du 6 octobre dernier tenue par vidéoconférence. Les membres du Comité ont apprécié la présentation du projet.

Ainsi, lors de cette réunion, le CÉR a procédé à l'évaluation éthique de votre projet précité. À cette fin, les documents suivants ont été examinés :

- Lettre de présentation au CÉR datée du 10 juillet 2020 ;
- Formulaire A;
- Formulaire d'évaluation de l'Institut universitaire sur la réadaptation en déficience physique de Montréal du CIUSSS du Centre-Sud-de-l'Île-de-Montréal daté du 15 septembre 2020, mentionnant que le projet est acceptable sur le plan de la convenance institutionnelle;
- Formulaire d'évaluation du CISSS de Laval daté du 24 septembre 2020, mentionnant que le projet est acceptable sur le plan de la convenance institutionnelle;
- Correspondance du 13 février 2020 suite à l'évaluation scientifique;
- Preuve d'octroi d'une subvention de 30 000 \$;
- Protocole de recherche;
- Formulaire d'information et de consentement (versions française et anglaise);
- Questionnaire STAI sur l'anxiété (versions française et anglaise);
- Questionnaire sur le bien-être général (versions française et anglaise);
- Questionnaire Échelle visuelle analogique;
- Questionnaire EQ5 (versions française et anglaise);
- Questionnaire Évaluation du stress (versions française et anglaise);
- Questionnaire Examen de Folstein sur l'état mental (versions française et anglaise);
- Questionnaire Échelle gériatrique de dépression (GDS) (versions française et anglaise);

Comité désigné en vertu de l'article 21 du Code civil du Québec

- Questionnaire Montreal cognitive assessment (MoCA) (versions française et anglaise);
- Questionnaire Inventaire multidimensionnel de la fatigue (IMF) (versions française et anglaise);
- Curriculum vitae de Louis Bherer;
- Curriculum vitae de Olivier Beauchet;
- Curriculum vitae de Simone Dalla Bella.

À la suite de son évaluation du projet, le CÉR vous demande d'apporter certaines modifications aux documents suivants :

CHANGEMENTS À APPORTER AUX FORMULAIRES DE CONSENTEMENT

- Lorsque cela s'applique, veuillez faire également les modifications proposées au formulaire de consentement en version anglaise.
1. Logos
Remplacer le logo du CIUSSS du Centre-Sud par le logo « Québec-Drapeau » puisque deux établissements sont impliqués dans votre projet.
 2. Établissements participants
Mettre cette rubrique au pluriel puisque deux établissements participent au projet et ajouter le CISSS de Laval puisque cet établissement a également répondu positivement à l'examen de convenance institutionnelle.
 3. Co-responsables du projet
Corriger la coquille « MontréalChercheur » par « Montréal – Chercheur ».
 4. Co-Chercheurs
 - Vous pourriez envisager de mettre les co-chercheurs en deux colonnes pour faciliter la mise en page et la lecture du formulaire ;
 - Puisque vous en avez parlé lors de votre présentation, il pourrait être intéressant de mentionner que votre projet a des collaborateurs hors-Québec, sans les nommer explicitement, en nommant seulement les pays impliqués ;
 - Pour monsieur Olivier Beauchet, veuillez franciser ses affiliations.
 5. Organismes subventionnaires
 - Veuillez mettre au pluriel le titre de la rubrique, car plusieurs organismes sont impliqués.
 6. Préambule
 - Quelques éléments sont redondants entre les rubriques « Préambule », « Description du projet et de ses objectifs » et « Nature de la participation ». Pour éviter le dédoublement de certaines informations et ainsi assurer la clarté du message, vous pourriez, par exemple, retirer la première partie de votre préambule qui mentionne l'adresse, le nombre de rencontres et l'objectif général;

- Si vous conservez cette phrase malgré la suggestion ci-haut mentionnée, veuillez corriger de la façon suivante : « divers aspects liés à la mobilité, à la cognition, au bien-être et à l'expérience ».

7. Nature de la participation

- Afin de clarifier la nature de ce qui est demandé au participant à l'intérieur des 60 minutes d'expérimentation, il serait intéressant d'être explicite sur le temps de la visite muséale et le temps des tests faits avant et après la visite ;
- Retirer ce qui est mentionné entre parenthèses, soit « (appareil fNIRS pour spectroscopie proche infrarouge fonctionnelle) » pour diminuer le langage technique;
- Comme une image vaut mille mots, il serait indiqué d'ajouter une image du dispositif d'imagerie cérébrale portable ainsi qu'une image des lunettes « Pupil ».

8. Risques et inconvénients pouvant découler de votre participation

- Veuillez ajouter le risque d'émotions négatives pouvant être entraîné par les tests de dépistage. Voici une suggestion de texte pouvant être ajouté : « Certaines questions ou certains tests pourraient vous faire vivre des émotions désagréables qui pourraient vous incommoder. Si cela survient, vous pourrez en discuter avec un membre de l'équipe de recherche qui pourra vous diriger vers des ressources appropriées ».
- Veuillez informer le CÉR des ressources qui seront remises au participant qui en ressentirait le besoin. Par exemple, un participant pourrait être préoccupé par son état cognitif suite à l'administration du MoCA ou du MMSE ou un participant pourrait être préoccupé par ses capacités physiques après la 2^e journée d'expérimentation.

9. Confidentialité

- À cette rubrique, vous mentionnez « Vos données pourraient être partagées avec des chercheurs membres de l'équipe de recherche qui résident à l'extérieur du Québec mais leur confidentialité sera toujours respectée. » De quelle façon sera fait ce partage? Quelles données seront transmises et sous quel format? Le CÉR souhaite vous rappeler que l'anonymisation n'est pas assurée seulement en retirant le nom du participant, et que, certains renseignements mis en commun peuvent constituer des renseignements identificatoires. Si vous avez des questions sur le sujet, vous pouvez vous référer au CÉR ou à l'Énoncé Politique des Trois Conseils (2018). Aussi, à propos des variables collectées, votre protocole mentionne l'analyse des variables socio-démographiques alors qu'aucun questionnaire de cette nature n'a été déposé. Pourriez-vous préciser quelles sont ces variables et où comptez-vous obtenir ces renseignements?

10. Indemnité compensatoire

- Vous pourriez reformuler la première phrase de la façon suivante : « Une indemnité totale de 20\$ vous sera remise en compensatoire de vos déplacements. L'admission au MBAM vous est offerte sans frais. »;
- Puisqu'il y a deux journées de présence au musée, vous pourriez envisager la possibilité de remettre l'indemnité compensatoire au prorata de la participation (10\$ à chaque visite).

11. Personnes-ressources

- Veuillez ajouter les coordonnées des commissaires locaux aux plaintes des deux établissements impliqués ainsi que le texte habituellement suggéré : « Pour ces

questions, vous pouvez aussi contacter le commissaire local aux plaintes de votre établissement : ».

PROCÉDURE DE RECRUTEMENT

- De quelle façon souhaitez-vous recruter des participants via les associations « Réseau Parkinson Québec » et « Association des aphasiques du Québec »? Veuillez fournir au CÉR votre document de recrutement, si applicable, en même temps que vos documents modifiés.
- Veuillez fournir le courriel de recrutement destiné aux membres VIP du MBAM.

CHOIX DES OUTILS

- Vous avez mentionné lors de votre présentation une ambivalence entre les membres de l'équipe de recherche face à l'utilisation du MoCA, du MMSE ou des deux outils. Dans l'idée de diminuer le fardeau d'administration au participant, il pourrait être intéressant de ne conserver qu'un seul de ces deux outils, selon le phénomène que vous souhaitez dépister (troubles neurocognitifs légers versus démence).

Par ailleurs, le CÉR tient à souligner que lors de la réalisation de votre étude, les mesures sanitaires en lien avec la pandémie de COVID-19 observées durant les séances d'expérimentation doivent faire l'objet d'une approbation par les différentes instances qui chapeautent les installations/locaux que vous utiliserez. **Comme votre expérimentation a lieu dans la communauté et implique des participants recrutés via des associations et le MBAM, veuillez fournir au CÉR votre plan de mitigation concernant les mesures sanitaires avant le début de votre expérimentation.**

Pour transmettre les modifications demandées, nous vous demandons de soumettre les **versions Word de vos documents en mode « suivi des modifications » que vous trouverez dans le volet « Révision »**, ou les versions Word avec les modifications surlignées jaune, à l'attention de Mme Kate Rousseau-Harrison à l'adresse suivante :

kate.rousseau-harrison.ccsmtl@ssss.gouv.qc.ca

Aussi, nous vous suggérons d'aller consulter sur la plateforme des projets de recherche la convenance institutionnelle de l'établissement ayant rendu une décision.

Si vous avez besoin de plus amples informations, nous vous invitons à communiquer avec :

Madame Kate Rousseau-Harrison
Coordonnatrice à l'éthique de la recherche des établissements du CRIR

Recevez, Madame, l'expression de nos meilleures salutations.

Me Michel T. Giroux
Président du comité d'éthique de la recherche
des établissements du CRIR
MG/krh

6.8 Annex: Case 5.2 AUTH (Greece)

Proof of ethics submission

Panagiotis Kartsidis <panos.kartsidis@gmail.com>

Αίτηση διεξαγωγής μελέτης JRA3 στα πλαίσια του έργου VITALISE

Ethics Committee RC AUTH <ethics@rc.auth.gr>
To: Panagiotis Kartsidis <panos.kartsidis@gmail.com>

Thu, Mar 17, 2022 at 2:03 PM

Καλησπέρα σας,

με το παρόν σας ενημερώνουμε ότι έχουμε λάβει την αίτησή σας και τα απαραίτητα συνοδευτικά έγγραφα της μελέτης JRA 3, η οποία θα διεξαχθεί στα πλαίσια του ερευνητικού έργου VITALISE.

Το αίτημά σας καταχωρήθηκε με αριθμό πρωτοκόλλου 68716/16-03-2022.

Στη διάθεσή σας για οποιαδήποτε πληροφορία ή διευκρίνιση.

Από τη Γραμματεία της ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ

Με εκτίμηση,
Ηράκλεια Καραγιαννιού

Γραμματεία της ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ
3ης Σεπτεμβρίου, Πανεπιστημιούπολη
54636, Θεσσαλονίκη, Ελλάδα
t: (+30) 2310998427
e: ethics@rc.auth.gr
u: <http://www.rc.auth.gr>

Διευκρίνιση ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου

Οι πληροφορίες που συμπεριλαμβάνονται σε αυτό το μήνυμα είναι εμπιστευτικές και η χρήση τους επιτρέπεται μόνον από τον αναφερόμενο παραλήπτη. Εάν έχετε λάβει το παρόν μήνυμα από λάθος και δεν είστε ο προοριζόμενος παραλήπτης, σας

Proof of ethics approval

ΑΡΙΣΤΟΤΕΛΕΙΟ
ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ
ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ

ΕΠΙΤΡΟΠΗ ΗΘΙΚΗΣ ΚΑΙ ΔΕΟΝΤΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ ΤΗΣ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ

Διεύθυνση: ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ
Πληροφορίες: Ηράκλεια Καραγιαννιού
Τηλ: 2310.998427
e-mail: ethics@rc.auth.gr

Θεσσαλονίκη, 28/03/2022
Αρ. Πρωτ.: 75071/2022

Τίτλος ερευνητικού έργου: «Ανοιχτές Ψηφιακές Υποδομές Ζωντανών Εργαστηρίων στον τομέα της Υγείας και της Ευεξίας»

Η Επιτροπή Ηθικής και Δεοντολογίας της Έρευνας του Αριστοτελείου Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλονίκης (ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ), στη Συνεδρίασή της με αριθμό 59/28-03-2022, αφού έλαβε υπόψη:

- α. την αίτηση του κ. Παναγιώτη Μπαμίδη, Καθηγητή του Τμήματος Ιατρικής της Σχολής Επιστημών Υγείας του ΑΠΘ (αρ. πρωτ. 68716/2022),
- β. τη Δήλωσή του ότι έλαβε γνώση του Κανονισμού Αρχών και Λειτουργίας της ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ και ότι αναλαμβάνει την υποχρέωση συμμόρφωσης και τήρησής του,
- γ. το υποβληθέν Ερευνητικό πρωτόκολλο,
- δ. το Ερωτηματολόγιο – έκθεση αυτοαξιολόγησης που προσκομίστηκε,
- ε. το έντυπο ενημερωμένης συγκατάθεσης που θα δοθεί στους συμμετέχοντες και
- στ. τις διατάξεις του Κανονισμού Αρχών και Λειτουργίας της ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ και της κείμενης νομοθεσίας,

αποφάσισε

την έγκριση διεξαγωγής της μελέτης με τίτλο **«Μελέτη επισκέψεων σε μουσείο»**, στα πλαίσια του έργου **«Ανοιχτές Ψηφιακές Υποδομές Ζωντανών Εργαστηρίων στον τομέα της Υγείας και της Ευεξίας (Vitalise)»**, καθώς κατά την κρίση της, τηρούνται οι παραδεκτοί κανόνες ηθικής και δεοντολογίας και ακεραιότητας της έρευνας ως προς το περιεχόμενο και ως προς τον τρόπο διεξαγωγής της, καθώς και οι εκ του νόμου προβλεπόμενες προϋποθέσεις.

Η παρούσα απόφαση της ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ σε καμία περίπτωση δεν υποκαθιστά άλλη απαιτούμενη έγκριση ή αδειοδότηση από άλλη αρμόδια δημόσια υπηρεσία, διοικητικό όργανο ή ανεξάρτητη διοικητική Αρχή, που δύναται επιπλέον να απαιτείται εκ του νόμου.

Ο Πρόεδρος της ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ

Dimitrios Stamovlasis
Digitally signed by Dimitrios Stamovlasis
Date: 2022.03.28 15:06:39 +03'00'

Δημήτριος Σταμοβλάσης

Αν. Καθηγητής Τμήματος Φιλοσοφίας και Παιδαγωγικής ΑΠΘ